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WOULD A SHIFT TO AGROECOLOGICAL SYSTEMS CHANGE DAIRY PRODUCTS' ROLE IN MEETING HUMAN NUTRITIONAL NEEDS?

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INTRODUCTION

Lever for tackling environmental challenges = farm agroecological transition

BUT unknown impact of this transition on contribution of dairy products to meeting human nutritional requirements

Aim of this study = to characterize the evolution of the population reference intake coverage by dairy products in France, when transitioning from conventional corn-based systems to organic grass-based systems.

METHODS

Calculation of the contribution of dairy products to nutrient recommended dietary intake according to the farming system (considering constant dairy consumption & all the milk produced with a same farming system)

French consumption of dairy products \times Concentration of nutrients in bulk milk / type of farming system

Data from EU H2020 project
intaqt
one quality

French consumption of nutrients through dairy products / type of farming system

EU Dietary reference values for each nutrient

INCA3, 2017; EFSA, 2019; WHO, 2023

RESULTS

Switching from a conventional corn-based to an organic grass-based system...

... had no major impact on the contribution of dairy products to meeting dietary reference values for minerals & vitamins B2/E

... tripled the contribution of dairy products to meeting dietary reference values for essential FA and *trans* FA*

*Limitation of *trans* FA in EU references

CONCLUSION & PERSPECTIVES

No major impact on minerals & B2/E vitamins
+++ Essential FA coverage (but ++ *trans* FA)

To be continued with other vitamins/oligo-minerals & other animal-based products